

Trans-[Coen₂H₂OCl]²⁺ (C) however appears not to react with B_z⁻ directly to produce either the *trans* form of D or D itself.

In their classic text book, Basolo and Pearson⁴ write that the reaction mechanism for the substitution of X⁻ by Y⁻ in [Coen₂X₂]⁺ ion always goes through the intermediate formation of the aquocomplex [Coen₂XH₂O]²⁺ i.e. in the following two steps-

- i) [Coen₂X₂]⁺ + H₂O → [Coen₂X.H₂O]²⁺ + X⁻
- ii) [Coen₂X.H₂O]²⁺ + Y⁻ → [Coen₂XY]⁺ + H₂O

the arguments being that the concentration of Y⁻ has no effect on the rate of Y⁻ entry and the aquation rate is the same as the X⁻ entry rate. Such a scheme would require that of the two consecutive steps i) and ii), i) is slow and ii) is very fast. However our study of the reaction ii) where Y⁻=B_z⁻ and X=Cl⁻ shows that ii) is a slow second-order reaction the rate of which depends on [B_z⁻] and the second order rate constant of which is pH-independent and given by k''=1.17 × 10⁻⁸ M⁻¹ Sec⁻¹ at 30° (vide Table 1) (ii) being a slow second order reaction; the scheme given by Basolo and Pearson in which (ii) is a very fast reaction independent of Y⁻ ion concentration becomes unacceptable. Moreover we have also shown that the *cis* and *trans* aquochlorocomplexes (B) and (C) are produced in large proportions simultaneously with the *p*-hydroxy benzoate substituted complex (D), when *cis*-[Coen₂Cl₂]⁺ reacts with B_z⁻ in 15% (v/v) ethanol-water medium. This would have not been the case if the substitution of water by B_z⁻ ion in (B) and (C) were very fast, since then only insignificant amount of (B) and (C) should have existed in solution, at any stage of the reaction. Our work clearly indicates that the substitution reaction occurs in two steps, the first slow step being the formation of the intermediate pentacoordinated [Coen₂X]²⁺ and the second fast step being the competitive capture of H₂O and B_z⁻ by this pentacoordinate intermediate. This type of mechanism in case of substitution of Cl⁻ from (A) by oxalate ligand had earlier been given by Ray and Siddhanta⁵. We believe that our work will serve to remove the age-old wrong idea that substitution in [Coen₂X₂]⁺ proceeds through an intermediate step of formation of the mono-aquo complex.

Experimental

(i) Preparation of compounds

Cis-[Coen₂Cl₂]⁺Cl, H₂O was prepared by the method given in the literature⁶. *Cis*-[Coen₂H₂OCl]²⁺SO₄ · 1.5H₂O, was prepared by the method of Werner⁷. They were characterised by elemental analysis and the study of absorption spectra.

(ii) Characterisation of products:

When (A) reacts with B_z⁻ ion it gives two types of products. When (A) and ammonium *p*-hydroxy benzoate are mixed in the molar ratio 1:3 and heated on a water bath a red crystalline product is formed, the composition

of which, as found by analysis, agrees with the formula [Coen₂B_z]₂B_z · 7H₂O. However, when the molar ratio is 1:1, heating the solution mixture on water bath ultimately produces a sticky mass, which on prolonged digestion with dehydrated alcohol and subsequent evaporation of alcohol at room temperature gives a product of composition [Coen₂B_zCl]Cl. To identify whether [Coen₂B_z]₂B_z · 7H₂O and [Coen₂B_zCl]Cl are of *cis* or *trans* variety, we have adopted the UV spectrophotometric method followed by Aprile, Caglioti and Illuminati⁸ and found that whereas [Coen₂B_z]₂B_z is of *trans* variety, [Coen₂B_zCl]Cl is however of *cis*-variety. These authors have reported that at ordinary temperature the reaction between (A) and silver-benzoate in 1:3 molar proportion results in the formation of *cis*-disubstituted product which at 60-65° isomerises into the *trans* variety. Our observation that the *trans* isomer of [Coen₂B_z]₂B_z · 7H₂O was produced was consistent with the above, since in our case the reaction was carried out on water bath presumably at a temperature more than 60°. UV absorption spectra of all these complexes along with that of *trans* chloro aquo complex is given in Fig 1.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of complexes 0.01 (M)
I—*Cis* [Coen₂Cl₂]⁺; II—*Cis* [Coen₂H₂OCl]²⁺; III—*Trans* [Coen₂H₂OCl]²⁺; IV—*Cis* [Coen₂B_zCl]⁺ and V—*Trans* [Coen₂B_z]₂⁺; Cell=2 cm.

We have also studied the reactions between *trans* [Coen₂Cl₂]⁺Cl and ammonium *p*-hydroxy benzoate taken in proportions 1:3 and 1:1 and found that products of the reactions are *trans* [Coen₂B_z]₂B_z · 7H₂O and D respectively same as those obtained from *cis* [Coen₂Cl₂]⁺Cl. The products *trans*-[Coen₂B_z]₂B_z and D have been obtained from reactions of the *cis*-chloro aquo-complex B with ammonium-*p*-hydroxybenzoate taken in proportions 1:3 and 1:1 respectively. The results of the study of the Cl⁻ ion substitution reactions in *trans*-[Coen₂Cl₂]⁺Cl by *p*-hydroxy-benzoate ion will be communicated soon.

(iii) Study of the Kinetics:

The steric course of the Cl⁻ substitution in (A) by B_z⁻ ion was studied part by part and the complete study comprises of the following six parts (a) to (f)

discussed below.

[All the following studies were carried out in 15% (v/v) ethanol at a temperature 30° and pH=3. Lowering of pH to 3 was done to prevent the formation of aquo-hydroxo product and subsequent isomerisation⁹. The solvent was 15% ethanol, because in aqueous medium at this pH solid *p*-hydroxy benzoic acid begins to precipitate from 0.2 (M) solution of NH₄B_s used in the study.]

(a) *Potentiometric determination of Cl⁻ ion release from (A) in presence and absence of B_s⁻ : (T=30°C ; pH=3) :*

The rate of Cl⁻ ion release from (A) was measured potentiometrically by noting the E. M. F. of the cell Satd. Calomel/NH₄NO₃ salt-bridge/Thermostated Reaction Mixture/AgCl, Ag, time to time and using a standard calibration curve previously drawn by plotting E.M.F. vs Cl⁻ ion concentration of KCl solutions of known strengths. The rate constant for the Cl⁻ ion release was obtained by Guggenheim plot, i.e. plot of log (Cl_{t+Δt} - Cl_t) vs time [where Cl_{t+Δt} and Cl_t are the concentrations of Cl⁻ ion at time (t + Δt) and t respectively and Δt is a constant time interval]. It was found that the rate constant remains the same both in presence and absence of ligand B_s⁻. The results are

TABLE 1

(All studies reported in this table were made at a temperature 30°C.)

(a) *Potentiometric Study.*

pH=3 ; solvent=15% (v/v) ethanol.
Rate constant for Cl⁻ ion release i.e. the rate constant for the reaction (Coen₂Cl₂)⁺→(Coen₂Cl)²⁺+Cl⁻ ;
k=2.49×10⁻⁴/Sec.
(Same in presence and absence of B_s⁻)

(b) *Isomerisation reaction.*

(k₄+k₅)=1.53×10⁻⁴/Sec. at pH=3 and in 15% (v/v) ethanol. k₄/k₅=0.40. Hence k₄=0.44×10⁻⁴/Sec. and k₅=1.09×10⁻⁵/Sec.

(c) *Spectrophotometric study of aquation of A.*

From Fig. 2 $L_t B_t / C_t = 1.9 = k'_1 / k'_2$.

But (k'₁+k'₂)=2.49×10⁻⁴/Sec. Hence k'₁=1.63×10⁻⁴/Sec. and k'₂=0.86×10⁻⁴/Sec.

(d) *The reaction B+B_s⁻→D+H₂O.*

At pH=4.2, k_{o b s}=2.223×10⁻⁵/Sec, from which pH independent second order rate constant k''=1.17×10⁻³ litre mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹ from where k₆ at pH=3 is 1.76×10⁻⁶/Sec. pK_a=4.83 (determined by Irving Rossotti method¹⁰ under the experimental condition.)

(e) *The reaction D+H₂O→B+B_s⁻.*

From the first order plot k₇=5.04×10⁻⁵/Sec.

(f) *Reaction involving entry of B_s⁻ in A.*

From the spectrophotometric reading at 30 minutes D_t/B_t=k₂/k₁=0.18.
C_t/B_t=k₃/k₁=0.35 ; but (k₁+k₂+k₃)=2.49×10⁻⁴/Sec. Therefore k₁=1.63×10⁻⁴/Sec. k₂=0.57×10⁻⁴/Sec. and k₃=0.29×10⁻⁴/Sec.

given in Table 1. This result suggests that the substitution of the first Cl⁻ ion in A by either H₂O or B_s⁻ proceeds through the same slow step namely the formation of the pentaco-ordinate intermediate [Coen₂Cl]²⁺.

(b) *Isomerisation of Cis-[Coen₂H₂OCl]²⁺ ion to trans form :*

Baldwin, Chan and Tobe⁸ have determined spectrophotometrically the values of k₄ and k₅ for the above reversible reaction at 25° and in 0.01(M) HNO₃. We have also determined k₄ and k₅ for the same reaction spectrophotometrically using the same method but at 30°, pH=3 and in 15% (v/v) ethanol-water mixture. Spectrophotometric study was made at 510 mμ where there is a maximum difference between the O.D. of the two isomers. The plot of log (D_∞-D_t) against time gave a straight line with slope (k₄+k₅) and the ratio of concentrations of C to B after attainment of equilibrium between the two gave k₄/k₅ ; the values of k₄ and k₅ were then calculated out. The results are given in Table 1.

(c) *Spectrophotometric study of the aquation of (A) and combination of this result with the results of (a). (T=30°C ; pH=3) :*

The fraction of (C) produced at different times during aquation of (A) in absence of B_s⁻ was determined by noting the change in O.D. of the solution at 525 mμ at different times. At this wave length ε_A=ε_B=89.2 and ε_C=13.2, hence the fractions of (C) were directly determined from the change in O.D. and the concentration C_t of C at time t could be calculated out. The concentrations B_t of B at different times t were calculated from the total chloride ion concentration (Cl_t) obtained from study (a) using the relation.

$$Cl_t = A_0 + B_t + C_t$$

Where A₀ is the initial concentration of A. The results are tabulated in Table 3. It will be seen from Table 3, last column that even from the beginning of the aquation reaction, the proportions of the *trans* product in comparison with the *cis* is not negligible ; at the end of the first ten minutes *trans* : *cis* ratio is 4:7.6. This contradicts the findings of Baldwin, Chan and Tobe⁸ that the *cis* dichloro complex (A) aquates to *cis* aquochlorocomplex with 100% retention of configuration. It is more reasonable to conclude that the *cis* dichloro complex aquates by two parallel paths to both *cis* and *trans* monoaquo complexes according to the scheme IB.

(Scheme IB)

From the potentiometric study of the Cl^- ion release in absence of B_s^- [study (a)] the overall rate constant k for this reaction was found out. It is evident that this k is the sum of the two individual rate constants k_1' and k_2' for the parallel reactions $\text{A} \rightarrow \text{B}$ and $\text{A} \rightarrow \text{C}$ (Scheme IB) i.e. $k = k_1' + k_2'$.

Had there been no interconversion between B and C, the ratio k_1'/k_2' would have been equal to B_t/C_t for any time t , since B and C are the only two products of the parallel reaction. But since the interconversion of B and C influences the ratio B_t/C_t and this influence becomes greater and greater as more and more B and C accumulates with time, the true value of k_1'/k_2' can be found out by extrapolating the values of B_t/C_t at different times to zero time i.e. using the relation—

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{\text{B}_t}{\text{C}_t} = \frac{k_1'}{k_2'}$$

The ratios B_t/C_t have been plotted against t in Fig. 2, and the curve has been extrapolated to $t=0$. The ratio B_t/C_t at $t=0$ gives $\frac{k_1'}{k_2'}$. Thus from the values of $(k_1' + k_2')$ and k_1'/k_2' , k_1' and k_2' have been calculated. The results are given in Table 1.

Fig. 2. Plot of B_t/C_t against time.

The activation parameters ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger for the chloride release reaction i. e. the reaction

were determined by studying potentiometrically the chloride release rate constant k at different temperatures using the Eyring equation (Table 2).

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE STEP $(\text{Coen}_2\text{Cl}_2)^+ \xrightarrow{k} (\text{Coen}_2\text{Cl})^{2+} + \text{Cl}^-$.

	25°C.	30°C	35°C	40°C
$k \times 10^4/\text{Sec.}$	1.51	2.49	3.62	6.72

From Eyring Equation $\Delta H^\ddagger = 19.87 \text{ K.cal/mole}$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger = -9.85 \text{ e.u.}$

(d) Spectrophotometric study of the entry of B_s^- in B:

The ligand dependance of the rate of this reaction was inferred from the fact that the rate of the forward reaction increases with increase in pH ; B_s^- concentration increases with increase of pH consequent on the shift of the equilibrium $\text{HB}_s \rightleftharpoons \text{H}^+ + \text{B}_s^-$ to the right and the rate of the reaction increases accordingly. We could not however study the reaction at pH 3 since the rate of the reaction was observed to be very slow. We, however studied the reaction by adjusting the pH to 4.2, so that the reaction rate became faster due to increase in concentration of the reacting B_s^- at this pH . (We used NH_4B_s as the source of the reacting B_s^- ion in the reaction.) The pH value remained constant at 4.2, due to the self-buffering action of NH_4B_s^* .

The reaction was followed spectrophotometrically at $460 \text{ m}\mu$ (at which wave-length $\epsilon_B = \epsilon_C$) using large excess of NH_4B_s . Neglecting the influence of the backward reaction at the early stages, the pseudo-first order rate constant k_{obs} was determined by plotting $\log \frac{D_\infty - D_0}{D_\infty - D_t}$ against time, upto first 90 minutes. The O.D. of pure D was taken as D_∞ .

The following considerations show that the reactive entity at any pH is B_s^- and not undissociated HB_s . It will be seen from the following results that the ratio of k_{obs} at pH 4.2 to k_{obs} at pH 4.6 is equal to the ratio of $[\text{B}_s^-]$ at pH 4.2 to $[\text{B}_s^-]$ at pH 4.6 and unequal to $\frac{[\text{HB}_s] \text{ at } \text{pH} 4.2}{[\text{HB}_s] \text{ at } \text{pH} 4.6}$. The results show that

the rate of B_s^- entry into the complex is proportional to $[\text{B}_s^-]$ and not to $[\text{HB}_s^-]$. This conclusion is further

*According to the Basolo and Pearson¹¹ the equilibrium constant for the reaction $-\text{[Coen}_2\text{ClH}_2\text{O}]^{2+} + \text{OH}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{[Coen}_2\text{ClOH}]^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ is 10^8 at 25° . The temperature coefficient of equilibrium constants in general being small, the equilibrium concentration of hydroxochlorospecies is expected to be about 1% of the concentration of the chloro-aquo species at pH 4.2 and 30° . As such base hydrolysis of B at pH 4.2 will not seriously alter the rate of the reaction $\text{B} + \text{B}_s^- \rightarrow \text{D} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ at this pH .

supported by the fact that at pH 3 where $[B_s^-]$ is very small and $[HB_s]$ is in large excess the reaction of $[B_s^-]$ entry into the complex is too slow to be measured. The rate of the reaction at pH 3 should have been faster than at pH 4.2 or 4.6 if $[HB_s]$ was the reactive species.

$$\frac{[B_s^-] \text{ at pH 4.2}}{[B_s^-] \text{ at pH 4.6}} = 0.473 \quad \frac{[HB_s] \text{ at pH 4.2}}{[HB_s] \text{ at pH 4.6}} = 1.32$$

Both calculated from K_a for $HB_s = 4.83$

$$\frac{k_{obs} \text{ at pH 4.2}}{k_{obs} \text{ at pH 4.6}} = \frac{2.223 \times 10^{-5}}{4.44 \times 10^{-5}} = 0.5$$

So the above reaction is actually a second order one and the pseudo-first order rate constant k_{obs} is related to the second order rate constant k'' by the relation—

$$k_{obs} = k''(B_s^-) = k'' \frac{K_a[HB_s]}{[H^+]}$$

where K_a = dissociation constant of HB_s .

By using the value of K_{obs} at pH 4.2, the second order pH independent rate constant k'' was calculated, whence the value of k_{obs} at pH 3 i.e. k_6 was calculated using the same equation. The results are given in Table 1.

(e) Spectrophotometric study of the aqution of D :

The above reaction was studied spectrophotometrically in 15% (v/v) ethanol (pH=3) and at 30° at 620 mμ. The first-order-rate constant k_7 was obtained by plotting $\log \frac{D_\alpha - D_0}{D_\alpha - D_t}$ against time for the first 90 minutes, assuming that the backward reaction $B + B_s^- \rightarrow D + H_2O$ is unimportant at this stage. O.D. of pure B was taken as D_α . In this case pH increases to 3.3 at the end. The results are given in Table 1.

(f) Spectrophotometric study of the entry of B_s^- in A : (T=30°C ; pH=3)

When (D) was allowed to react with B_s^- (actually NH_4B_s at pH 3) at 30°, the O.D. values of the solution at 550 mμ, (at which wave length there is a substantial difference in O.D. between D and *cis* 1:3 or *trans* 1:3 product) were measured from time to time ; we found that O.D. remains constant with time, which means that under this condition practically no *cis* or *trans* 1:3 product is produced.

Next we studied the aqution of D. We found that O.D. of a solution of D changes with time at 620 mμ (Here $\epsilon_B=8$ and $\epsilon_D=23$), but a potentiometric study with Ag/AgCl electrode indicates that no Cl^- ion is

released. It means that in the aqution of (D), the B_s^- ion rather than Cl^- ion in (D) is replaced by H_2O producing $[Coen_2H_2OCl]^{2+}$. Now to see whether this chloroaquo complex is (B) or (C), we studied the same aqution at 510 mμ (at this wave length $\epsilon_B \approx \epsilon_D = 84$ and $\epsilon_C = 13$) and found that O.D. remains constant with time, this means aqution of (D) produces (B) only and not (C) at all, so that it is an equilibrium between only (B) and (D) [as established in the studies (d) and (e) above]. It is thus reasonable to believe that when (B) reacts with B_s^- , it produces D only and there is 100% retention of configuration.

In order to obtain the amounts of (B), (C) and (D) and unreacted (A) at the different stages of the reaction of B_s^- entry in A, we have followed the reaction spectrophotometrically at three different wave lengths viz. 525 mμ, 450 mμ and 630 mμ simultaneously. At 525 mμ $\epsilon_A = \epsilon_B \approx \epsilon_D = 89.5$ and $\epsilon_C = 13$, so fall in O.D. at different stages of the reaction gave the concentrations of (C) directly at those stages.

Again at 450 mμ ($\epsilon_A \approx \epsilon_B = 20.5$; $\epsilon_C = 30$ and $\epsilon_D = 71$), so concentration of (D) will be known from the equation—

$$\Delta d_t = \frac{C_t}{A_0} (\epsilon_C - \epsilon_A) + \frac{D_t}{A_0} (\epsilon_D - \epsilon_A)$$

O.D. of the reaction mixture at time t - O.D. of A at Conc. A_0
where $\Delta d_t = \frac{\text{length of the cell} \times A_0$

A_0 = Initial concentration of A.

C_t being known from the study at 525 mμ, D_t will be known from the above equation.

At 630 mμ ($\epsilon_A = 32.5$; $\epsilon_B = 6.7$; $\epsilon_C = 20$; $\epsilon_D = 17.5$). So B_t can be known from the measured value of Δd_t at 630 mμ, using the equation—

$$\Delta d_t = \frac{B_t}{A_0} (\epsilon_B - \epsilon_A) + \frac{C_t}{A_0} (\epsilon_C - \epsilon_A) + \frac{D_t}{A_0} (\epsilon_D - \epsilon_A)$$

Thus B_t , C_t and D_t being known, A_t can be determined from the relation—

$$A_0 = A_t + B_t + C_t + D_t$$

Results and Discussion

We started our study by first considering simply the aqution of A in absence of B_s^- and proved that both B and C are produced simultaneously by aqution and at the same time B and C produced are interconverted according to the Scheme IB.

Scheme IB was established by the following approximate method of calculating A_t , B_t and C_t at different times t, using the rate constant values obtained

from studies (a), (b) and (c) and comparing these values with experimentally determined ones of A_t , B_t and C_t (vide Table 3).

TABLE 3—COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND CALCULATED VALUES OF (B) AND (C) PRODUCED DURING AQUATION OF A. INITIAL CONCENTRATION OF A=0.01 (M)

Time (t) (mins.)	TRANS AQUO (C_t) M		CIS AQUO (B_t) M		Exptl. B_t/C_t
	Exptl.	Calcd.	Exptl.	Calcd.	
10	0.0005	0.00052	0.00096	0.00098	1.93
20	0.0010	0.00094	0.00195	0.0018	1.95
30	0.0013	0.0013	0.0026	0.0025	2.00
40	0.0016	0.0016	0.0033	0.0032	2.04
50	0.0018	0.0018	0.0039	0.0037	2.10
60	0.0020	0.0021	0.0042	0.0041	2.13
70	0.0022	0.0022	0.0048	0.0045	2.15

In our approximate calculation, we assumed that the concentration of A remains almost constant i.e. $\approx A_0$, during a brief span of time (say 10 minutes) just after the initiation of the reaction. During this period we may also neglect the equilibrium between B and C, and obtain—

$$\frac{\Delta B}{\Delta t} = k_1' A_0 \text{ and } \frac{\Delta C}{\Delta t} = k_2' A_0$$

$$\text{Therefore } \Delta B = k_1' A_0 \Delta t \text{ and } \Delta C = k_2' A_0 \Delta t$$

Since initial concentrations of B and C were zero therefore $\Delta B =$ concentration of B after first 10 minutes $= B_{10}$ and $\Delta C =$ concentration of C after first 10 minutes $= C_{10}$. So concentration of A after first ten minutes $= (A_0 - B_{10} - C_{10}) = A_{10}$.

During the next ten minutes we assumed that concentration of A, B and C remain almost constant at A_{10} , B_{10} and C_{10} respectively. And here taking into consideration the interconversion of B and C also we get from Scheme IB

$$\frac{\Delta B''}{\Delta t} = k_1' A_{10} - k_4 B_{10} + k_5 C_{10}$$

and

$$\frac{\Delta C'}{\Delta t} = k_2' A_{10} - k_5 B_{10} + k_4 B_{10}$$

Thus $\Delta B''$ and $\Delta C'$ will be known and hence the concentrations of B and C after this 10 minutes i.e. 20 minutes after the beginning will be—

$$B_{20} = B_{10} + \Delta B''; C_{20} = C_{10} + \Delta C' \text{ and hence}$$

$$A_{20} = (A_0 - B_{20} - C_{20}).$$

(In this calculation, the less the time interval chosen, the greater will be the accuracy.)

In this way we calculated the values of A, B and C at different times and compared those values with the experimental values obtained during the study of aquation. The agreement is excellent (Table 3). It proves conclusively that aquation of A produces B and C simultaneously and at the same time B and C are interconverted.

From the above Scheme IB it is evident that the *cis*-complex A produces a pentacoordinate intermediate I_1 (Fig. 3) part of which immediately captures H_2O in a fast reaction to produce *cis* chloroaquo product B (k_1 path) and the rest of which in a simultaneous comparative fast reaction isomerise into the pentacoordinate intermediate I_2 (Fig. 3) and captures an H_2O molecule as if in a single step to produce *trans* aquochloro product C (k_2 path). The values of activation parameters $\Delta H^\ddagger = 19.9$ K.cal/mole and $\Delta S^\ddagger = -9.9$ e.u. are in conformity with this view, since

Fig. 3. Pentacoordinate intermediates I_1 and I_2 .

- i) $\Delta H^\ddagger =$ ca. 20 K.cal/mole is of the order of M-Cl covalent bond breaking energy, and
- ii) the negative value of entropy of activation may be assigned to the development of the products $(Coen_2Cl)^{2+}$ and Cl^- from $(Coen_2Cl_2)^+$ signifying a more electrostricted activated complex as compared to the reactant entity.

After establishing the scheme IB we tried to propose a scheme for the reaction involving the entry of B_z^- in A. As Basolo and Pearson⁴ have reported that with the single exception of OH^- there is no good evidence for any direct reaction of a nucleophilic reagent with a $Co(III)$ complex in water solution and that the mechanism for the substitution proceeds in all cases through the intermediate formation of an aquo-complex, we considered the following scheme (Scheme III), in which the B_z^- substituted complex (D) is formed not directly from (A), but from the aquo-complex B [it has already been concluded from the study (f) that (D) is produced from B only and not from (C)].

We next calculated A_t , B_t , C_t and D_t at different times during the reaction course, using the already determined k values and following the above scheme. However, these calculated values differ widely (Table 4) from the spectrophotometrically determined values. The discrepancies become wider in case of D_t , where the calculated values are extremely small in comparison to the experimental values. These led us to the belief that D may be produced directly from A in addition to its being produced from B . This path seemed plausible as the first dissociative slow step of the reaction is the formation of penta-coordinate intermediate $[\text{Coen}_2\text{Cl}]^{2+}$

Assuming that during the first 10 minutes of the reaction B , C and D are produced exclusively from A and that interconversions between B to C and between B to D can be neglected, we have

$$\frac{\Delta B}{\Delta t} = k_1 A_0; \quad \frac{\Delta C}{\Delta t} = k_2 A_0 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\Delta D}{\Delta t} = k_3 A_0 \quad \text{and so}$$

$$B_{10} = \Delta B = k_1 A_0 \Delta t$$

$$C_{10} = \Delta C = k_2 A_0 \Delta t$$

$$D_{10} = \Delta D = k_3 A_0 \Delta t \quad \text{and}$$

$$A_{10} = A_0 - (B_{10} + C_{10} + D_{10})$$

TABLE 4 - COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND CALCULATED (ACCORDING TO SCHEME III) VALUES OF A_t , B_t , C_t AND D_t .

$A_0 = 0.01$ (M) concentration of $\text{NH}_4\text{B}_x = 0.1$ (M), $\text{pH} = 3$.

Time (mins)	$A_t \times 10^3$ (M)		$B_t \times 10^3$ (M)		$C_t \times 10^3$ (M)		$D_t \times 10^3$ (M)	
	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
30	5.9	6.1	2.7	2.54	0.89	1.32	0.49	0.003
60	3.6	3.76	4.4	4.13	1.45	2.06	0.78	0.012
90	2.6	2.33	4.9	5.15	1.80	2.49	0.83	0.025
120	2.0	1.44	5.2	5.80	2.10	2.72	0.90	0.040
150	1.4	0.92	5.4	6.22	2.2	2.84	0.96	0.055

from A and there is every possibility of a competitive capture of both B_x^- and H_2O by this intermediate. It cannot also be doubted that this penta-coordinate intermediate is also formed from B in the first slow dissociative step which then captures competitively the ligands H_2O and B_x^- giving rise to the equilibrium $\text{B} \rightleftharpoons \text{D}$. So we have been forced to propose the Scheme II as the only plausible mechanism.

We then calculated theoretically the amounts of A , B , C and D at different stages of the reaction according to Scheme II using our experimental k -values. We already know the values k_4 , k_5 , k_6 and k_7 (as per Scheme II) from studies 'c', 'd' and 'e'; the values of k_1 , k_2 and k_3 (as per Scheme II) were determined in the following way. If Scheme II is correct, then

$$(k_1 + k_2 + k_3) = \text{Rate constant } k \text{ for the } \text{Cl}^- \text{ ion release from } A \text{ in presence of } \text{B}_x^-.$$

At the early stage of the reaction (first 30 minutes) we may take $k_1 : k_2 : k_3 = [\text{B}_t] : [\text{C}_t] : [\text{D}_t]$. B_t , C_t and D_t for $t=30$ mins were found out spectrophotometrically (study 'f'), whence $k_1 : k_2 : k_3$ was known; $k = k_1 + k_2 + k_3$ was experimentally found out from the potentiometric study and hence the individual values of k_1 , k_2 and k_3 could be known.

During the next 10 minutes, interconversions between B to C and between B to D also are taken in account and we write

$$\frac{\Delta B'}{\Delta t} = k_1 A_{10} - k_4 B_{10} - k_6 B_{10} + k_5 C_{10} + k_7 D_{10}$$

$$\frac{\Delta C'}{\Delta t} = k_2 A_{10} - k_5 C_{10} + k_4 B_{10}$$

$$\frac{\Delta D'}{\Delta t} = k_3 A_{10} - k_7 D_{10} + k_6 B_{10}$$

So that

$$\text{B}_{20} = \text{B}_{10} + \Delta B'; \quad \text{C}_{20} = \text{C}_{10} + \Delta C' \quad \text{and} \quad \text{D}_{20} = \text{D}_{10} + \Delta D'$$

$$\text{and } A_{20} = A_0 - (\text{B}_{20} + \text{C}_{20} + \text{D}_{20})$$

In this way concentration of (A), (B), (C) and (D) at different stages of the reaction was calculated. These calculated values agree very well with the corresponding spectrophotometrically determined values of A_t , B_t , C_t and D_t as obtained from study (f) and given in Table 5. Also the concentration of the total Cl^- ion at different stages of the reaction as calculated from the spectrophotometrically obtained values of (A), (B), (C) and (D) at the corresponding stages agrees excellently with the corresponding values obtained by independent potentiometric study. The results are shown in Table 5. The difference between the calculated and experimental values of A_t , B_t , C_t , D_t and Cl_t is seldom greater than 10%; the agreement should be regarded as quite good in view of the approximate nature of the experimental procedure and of the method of calculation.

TABLE 5—COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND CALCULATED (ACCORDING TO THE SCHEME II) VALUES OF A_t , B_t , C_t AND D_t . INITIAL CONCENTRATION OF $A=0.01 (M)$ $C_{NH_4B_4}=0.10 (M)$, $pH=3$.

Time (t) (mins)	$B_t (M)$		$C_t (M)$		$D_t (M)$		$A_t (M)$		Total $Cl^-_t (M)$	
	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Spectro- photome- tric	Poten- tiome- tric
30	0.0025	0.0027	0.0009	0.0009	0.0004	0.0005	0.0062	0.0059	0.0141	0.0130
60	0.0041	0.0044	0.0015	0.0013	0.0007	0.0008	0.0038	0.0036	0.0165	0.0151
90	0.0050	0.0049	0.0018	0.0016	0.0008	0.0008	0.0024	0.0026	0.0173	0.0168
120	0.0056	0.0052	0.0021	0.0019	0.00085	0.0009	0.0015	0.0020	0.0178	0.0180
150	0.0059	0.0054	0.0022	0.0021	0.0009	0.0010	0.0010	0.0014	0.0181	0.0190

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